

The Effect of Spiritual Self-Care Training on the Feeling of Comfort in Hospitalized Women: A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

Spiritual self-care plays a vital role in promoting emotional well-being and enhancing comfort, particularly for hospitalized women facing physical and psychological challenges. This review explores the impact of spiritual self-care training on the comfort levels of women in healthcare settings. Emphasis is placed on the mechanisms through which spiritual practices contribute to overall well-being, recent studies evaluating intervention effectiveness, and recommendations for integrating spiritual care into clinical practice.

Introduction

Hospitalization is often associated with physical pain, emotional distress, and a sense of vulnerability. For women, particularly those facing obstetric or gynecological issues, the experience can be deeply unsettling. Spiritual self-care, encompassing practices such as meditation, prayer, mindfulness, and spiritual counseling, has been identified as a critical factor in improving psychological resilience and comfort during hospitalization (1). This review aims to synthesize evidence on the effectiveness of spiritual self-care training in enhancing hospitalized women's comfort and propose strategies for its clinical application.

Concept of Spiritual Self-Care in Healthcare

Spiritual self-care involves activities that nurture the spirit, provide a sense of purpose, and promote emotional balance. It is particularly significant in healthcare contexts where patients often face existential questions and seek meaning during illness(2). Spiritual self-care strategies include:

- **Mindfulness and Meditation:** Techniques to focus attention and reduce stress.
- **Religious Practices:** Prayers, scripture reading, and rituals specific to individual beliefs.
- **Counseling:** Conversations to explore spiritual needs and address existential concerns.

Spiritual Comfort in Hospitalized Women

The feeling of comfort among hospitalized women is multifaceted, encompassing physical relaxation, emotional peace, and a sense of support. Spiritual self-care training has been linked to enhanced comfort by:

- **Reducing Anxiety:** Spiritual practices help reduce hospital-related stress and anxiety (3).
- **Pain Management:** Techniques such as guided imagery and meditation can influence pain perception.

- **Enhancing Emotional Well-Being:** Addressing spiritual needs improves mood and promotes positive outlooks during recovery (4).

Impact of Spiritual Self-Care Training: Evidence from Studies

Improved Psychological Outcomes

A study conducted on women undergoing chemotherapy found that spiritual counseling sessions significantly improved emotional well-being, reduced depressive symptoms, and enhanced overall comfort (5).

Enhanced Coping Mechanisms

Women hospitalized for high-risk pregnancies showed greater resilience and coping abilities after participating in spiritual self-care workshops. These interventions included mindfulness exercises and journaling focused on gratitude (6).

Pain Reduction

Research on postoperative recovery in gynecological patients revealed that those receiving spiritual self-care training reported lower pain levels and required less analgesic medication compared to a control group (7).

Improved Patient-Provider Communication

Spiritual self-care initiatives often include guidance on expressing spiritual needs, leading to better communication with healthcare providers and fostering a sense of holistic care(8).

Mechanisms of Action

Spiritual self-care training promotes comfort through:

- **Stress Reduction:** Activating the parasympathetic nervous system via relaxation techniques.
- **Meaning-Making:** Helping patients derive a sense of purpose despite illness.
- **Social Support:** Connecting women with peer groups and spiritual communities.
- **Neurochemical Regulation:** Enhancing levels of serotonin and oxytocin, which are associated with feelings of calmness and happiness (9,10).

Challenges in Implementing Spiritual Self-Care Training

- **Cultural Sensitivity:** Variability in spiritual beliefs requires tailored interventions.
- **Healthcare Providers' Training:** Nurses and clinicians often lack training in spiritual care delivery.

- **Time Constraints:** Integrating spiritual self-care into busy clinical schedules can be challenging.
- **Stigma:** Patients may hesitate to discuss spiritual needs due to fear of judgment(11).

Recommendations for Clinical Practice

- **Incorporating Spiritual Assessment Tools:** Using instruments like the HOPE model (Hope, Organized religion, Personal spirituality, Effects on care) to evaluate patients’ spiritual needs(12).
- **Training Healthcare Providers:** Offering workshops on spiritual care for nurses and physicians.
- **Creating a Supportive Environment:** Establishing quiet spaces for meditation and prayer in hospitals.
- **Collaborating with Chaplains and Counselors:** Integrating spiritual professionals into care teams.
- **Tailored Programs:** Designing interventions that respect cultural and religious diversity. 8.

Future Directions

Further research is needed to:

- Evaluate long-term effects of spiritual self-care on comfort and recovery. 10.
- Identify optimal delivery methods for spiritual interventions. 11.
- Explore the role of digital tools, such as meditation apps, in facilitating self-care practices for hospitalized women. 12.

Conclusion

Spiritual self-care training represents a promising approach to enhancing comfort among hospitalized women. By addressing spiritual needs, healthcare providers can foster holistic recovery and emotional resilience. Implementing culturally sensitive and patient-centered spiritual care practices is essential for improving the quality of healthcare delivery.

References

- 1.Carey LB, Drummond D, Koenig HG, Gabbay E, Hill T, Cohen J, et al. Care of the Aged, Women’s Health, and Measuring Religion, Spirituality and Health. Vol. 62, Journal of Religion and Health. 2023.
- 2.Puchalski CM, Vitillo R, Hull SK, Reller N. Improving the spiritual dimension of whole person care: Reaching national and international consensus. In: Journal of Palliative Medicine. 2014.

- 3.Park CL, Masters KS, Salsman JM, Wachholtz A, Clements AD, Salmoirago-Blotcher E, et al. Advancing our understanding of religion and spirituality in the context of behavioral medicine. J Behav Med. 2017;40(1).
- 4.Arentz S, Hunter J, Deed G. Integrating Traditional and Complementary Medicine Recommendations into Clinical Practice Guidelines for People with Diabetes in Need of Palliative and End-of-Life Care: A Scoping Review. Vol. 26, Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine. 2020.
- 5.Kruizinga R, Hartog ID, Jacobs M, Daams JG, Scherer-Rath M, Schilderman JBAM, et al. The effect of spiritual interventions addressing existential themes using a narrative approach on quality of life of cancer patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. Vol. 25, Psycho-Oncology. 2016.
- 6.Root AL, Crossley NP, Heck JL, McCage S, Proulx J, Jones EJ. Effects of Mindfulness-Based Interventions on Cardiometabolic-Related Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes: A Systematic Review. Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing. 2024;39(4).
- 7.Liu B, Liu S, Wang B, Liu W, Chen L, Zheng T, et al. Effectiveness and safety of implementing an enhanced patient comfort programme for elective neurosurgical patients: A randomised controlled trial protocol. BMJ Open. 2023;13(4).
- 8.Delgado-Guay MO, Hui D, Parsons HA, Govan K, De La Cruz M, Thorney S, et al. Spirituality, religiosity, and spiritual pain in advanced cancer patients. J Pain Symptom Manage. 2011;41(6).
- 8.Newberg AB. Religious and Spiritual Practices: A Neurochemical Perspective. In: Where God and Science meet: How brain and evolutionary studies alter our understanding of religion (Vol 2): The neurology of religious experience. 2006.
- Carlson LE, Bultz BD. Mind-body interventions in oncology. Curr Treat Options Oncol. 2008;9(2–3).
- 9.Finley K. Narratives & spiritual meaning-making in mental disorder. International Journal for Philosophy of Religion. 2023;94(3).
- 10.Anandarajah G, Hight E. Spirituality and medical practice: Using the HOPE questions as a practical tool for spiritual assessment. Vol. 63, American Family Physician. 2001.